

SHORT COMMUNICATION

Synthesis of Mesoionic 1,3,4-thiadiazoles

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Results of our physico-chemical investigations on heterocyclic systems containing -NCS group have been recently reported¹⁻³ by us. In continuation of this work, we wish to keep on record the syntheses of several 4-phenyl-5-aryl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazoles(I) which belong to the interesting group of pseudo-aromatic compounds^{4,5}, like well known sydnones⁵.

TABLE I

4-phenyl-5-aryl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazoles(I)*

No.	Ar.	M.P. °C	Colour	$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$	
				m μ . ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$)	m μ ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$)
1.	Ph ^a	228	Yellow	275 (19.8)	397 (5.24)
2.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ Ph	212-13 dec.	Orange-red	274 (28.98)	428 (5.50)
3.	<i>p</i> -IPh	219 dec.	,,	284 (20.32)	405 (6.29)
4.	<i>p</i> -BrPh	212-13	Yellow	280 (22.05)	405 (5.89)
5.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ Ph	227-28	Orange	~ 280 sh (18.38)	410 (4.46)
6.	<i>m</i> -ClPh	191-92	,,	273 (18.73)	405 (4.87)
7.	<i>m</i> -BrPh	196	Yellow	273 (19.92)	405 (5.33)
8.	<i>m</i> -EtOPh	185	,,	278 (17.27)	397(5.59)

*Satisfactory analyses have been obtained.

(a) Reported, ref. 6, m.p. 228-25°, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 275 m μ (ϵ , 18900) & 405 m μ (ϵ , 4600).

1. P. B. Talukdar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 17.
2. P. B. Talukdar and S. K. Sengupta, *ibid*, 1967, **44**, 104.
3. P. B. Talukdar and S. Banerjee, *ibid*, 1967, **44**, 1060.
4. L. B. Kier and E. B. Roche, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1967, **56**, 149.
5. F. H. C. Stewart, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 129.

The compounds reported herein were all obtained⁶ by reacting the appropriate aryl chloride with potassium phenyldithiocarbazinate under agitation at 100m temperature. After one crystallisation, the products were obtained as yellow to orange-yellow crystals as noted in Table I. From the results in Table I, it appears that the absorption spectra of the mesoionic thiadiazoles are characterised by two main bands around 275 and 405 μ , but the substituents in Ar are found to influence the position and intensity of the band indicating appreciable overlap of orbitals of the two planar rings. These and other aspects of the problem are proposed to be taken up in a subsequent communication.

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⁶: T. G. Stewart and L. B. Kier, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1965, **54**, 731.